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OF PUBLICATION

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For publishing in
Brio Innovative Journal of Novel Research (BIJNR)

“Revolutionizing Childbirth: The Role of Nurses in Supporting Water Births and Natural Labor”

Volume: 1

Issue: 2

Year:2024

Dr Bince V
Chief Editor

Pub ID: BIJNR202439

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